

(see table), followed by dinitramine, piperophos/2,4-D, propanil, and butachlor which provided statistically comparable control.

More panicles/m² were recorded for hand weeding, but results were similar to those with dinitramine and piperophos/2,4-D. Spikelets per panicle, 1,000-grain weight, and yield followed a similar trend. Diethatyl, butachlor, and oxy-fluorfen were most toxic to the crop. □

Table continued.

Treatment	Dose (kg ai/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Spikelets (no./panicle)	1000-grain (g)	Toxicity ^b 25 DS	Dry wt of weeds (g/m ²)
Propanil	3	3 b	299 b	107 a	26 ab	1.6 c	90 f
Hand weeding	25 & 50 DS	4 a	352 a	112 a	27 a	1.0 c	60 g
Unweeded control	–	2 f	153 c	68 c	23 d	1.0 c	453 a

^aIn a column means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

^bToxicity rating: 1 = no toxicity, 10 = complete kill, DS = days after sowing.

Soil and crop management

Dry matter yield reduction caused by sulfur-coated urea application to low percolation soils

C. S. Khind and M. F. Kazibwe, Soils Department, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana, India

Sulfur-coated urea (SCU) is a slow-release nitrogen (N) fertilizer which, when broadcast and incorporated before transplanting, can minimize N losses and improve N efficiency in lowland rice. However, soil texture, CEC, and percolation rate affect SCU efficiency. We studied the effect of SCU on dry matter yields and micro-nutrient concentration in rice plants in soils with and without good percolation.

The greenhouse experiment in 1982 kharif was on a sandy loam Typic Ustochrept with pH 8.5, EC 0.15 mmho/cm,

0.23% organic carbon, and 4.54 meq/100 g CEC. Ten-liter pots were filled with 8 kg of air-dried, sieved soil treated with 26 mg P and 50 mg K/kg. Soil was flooded, puddled, and treated with 115 mg N/kg as prilled urea splits (PUS), urea supergranule (USG), urea mudball (MBU), or SCU. USG and MBU were deep-placed at 5-7 cm. SCU was broadcast and incorporated at 5-7 cm. Four 27-day-old PR106 seedlings were planted in each pot. Pots were flooded to maintain 5 cm standing water. Percolation for appropriate pots was maintained at 5 mm/h using pinchcocks. Treatments were in a completely randomized design with three replications. Plants were harvested at 15, 30, 45, and 60 days after transplanting (DT) and dry matter yields were recorded. Zn, Fe, Mn, and Cu concentrations were determined for plants harvested at

60 DT.

Without percolation, dry matter yields, except at 15 DT, were less for SCU-treated plants than for PUS, MBU, and USG. With percolation, SCU-treated plants yielded significantly more dry matter at 60 DT than USG (Table 1). Dry matter yields from PUS and MBU equaled those from SCU.

Without percolation, SCU-treated plants generally had lower Zn, Fe, Mn, and Cu concentrations than other treatments (Table 2). With percolation, they had significantly higher Fe and Mn concentrations than USG. Plants with SCU, PUS, and MBU had similar Zn, Fe, Mn, and Cu concentrations. In the absence of percolation, sulfides of these metals or H₂S may have been formed and thus hindered micronutrient uptake and reduced dry matter yields. □

Table 1. Effect of percolation and urea fertilizer on rice dry matter yields.^a

Urea fertilizer	Dry matter yield at indicated days after transplanting (DT)									
	Without percolation					With percolation				
	g/hill				g/pot 60 DT	g/hill				g/pot 60 DT
15 DT	30 DT	45 DT	60 DT	15 DT		30 DT	45 DT	60 DT		
No N check	0.20	0.70	1.30	3.7	9.8 a	0.30	0.90	3.10	6.3	17.2 a
Prilled urea 3-split	0.50	2.95	5.90	17.6	37.2 c	0.50	2.20	6.10	15.0	36.3 b
Urea mudball	0.25	2.70	7.50	17.3	36.4 c	0.45	2.60	5.80	16.5	32.8 b
Urea supergranule	0.40	2.80	8.40	19.2	40.3 c	0.30	1.20	4.50	10.7	21.2 a
Sulfur-coated urea	0.35	1.80	4.30	12.5	29.3 b	0.25	2.20	5.50	18.7	32.9 b
Interaction ^b	–	–	–	–	(PXU)**	–	–	–	–	(PXU)**
CV (%)					9.9					9.9

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at $P = 0.05$, ^b** = significant at $P = 0.01$. P = percolation, U = urea material.

Table 2. Effect of percolation and urea fertilizer on micronutrient content of rice plants (60 DT).^a

Urea fertilizer	Micronutrients (ppm)							
	Without percolation				With percolation			
	Zn	Fe	Mn	Cu	Zn	Fe	Mn	Cu
Check	34.6 a	130 a	480 a	6.0 a	22.0 a	165 a	383 ab	4.0 a
Prilled urea 3-split	50.6 b	226 bc	591 bc	10.0 b	38.6 b	260 bc	421 ab	8.0 b
Urea mudball	53.0 b	240 c	580 bc	8.0 ab	39.3 b	256 bc	378 ab	6.0 ab
Urea supergranule	58.3 b	223 bc	651 c	9.3 b	35.3 b	231 b	343 a	7.3 b
Sulfur-coated urea	38.6 a	176 ab	545 ab	6.0 a	35.6 b	286 c	458 b	6.3 b
Interaction ^b	(PXU)**	(PXU)**	(PXU)**	(PXU)**	(PXU)**	(PXU)**	(PXU)**	(PXU)**
CV (%)	12.9	14.1	9.7	19.2	12.9	14.1	9.7	19.2

^a In a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at $P = 0.05$. ^b** = significant at $P = 0.01$, P = percolation, U = urea material.

Fertilizer trials in West Bengal

D. K. Das and S. J. Islam, AICPND, Purulia District, Bidhan Chandra Krishi Viswavidyalaya, West Bengal, India

We compared farmer fertilizer use levels with recommended levels in Purulia, West Bengal, in 1981 kharif. Soil characteristics at 6 demonstration sites varied from

pH 4.8 to 6.8, 0.28 to 0.83% organic matter, 5.5 to 38.1 kg available P/ha, and 116.2 to 160.5 kg available K/ha.

IET1444 (Rasi) was transplanted in rainfed fields at 4 fertilizer levels: farmer level of 20.0-4.4-8.3 kg NPK/ha; treatment 1, 27.0-7.0-12.4 kg NPK/ha; treatment 2, 45.0-8.4-20.8 kg NPK/ha; and treatment 3, 55.0-9.7-27.4 kg NPK/ha.

Treatment 3 yielded highest – 3.6 t/ha — (see table) but treatment 2, which yielded 3.4 t/ha, gave the highest benefit-cost ratio, 10.5. Economic analysis of treatments and yields showed that investing an extra \$11.23 to \$39.43/ha could increase returns from \$100.23 to \$311.62/ha. □

Economic analysis of added NPK compared to farmer fertilizer management level in Purulia, West Bengal.

Treatment	Fertilizer rate (kg/ha)			Yield range (t/ha)	Mean yield (t/ha)	Added yield over farmer level (t/ha)	Value of added yield (\$/ha)	Cost of added inputs ^a (\$/ha)	Added profit over farmer level (\$/ha)	Benefit: cost
	N	P	K							
Farmer level	20	4.4	8.3	0.94-1.15	1.07	—	—	—	—	—
1	27	7.0	12.4	1.62-2.05	1.86	0.79	111.46	11.23	100.23	8.9
2 ^b	45	8.4	20.8	3.12-3.65	3.36	2.29	323.01	28.14	294.87	10.5
3	55	9.7	27.4	3.46-3.61	3.56	2.49	351.05	39.43	311.62	7.9

^a Cost/kg of fertilizer – N:\$0.66, P:\$2.00, K:\$0.32; price of paddy/t = \$141.10. ^b Recommended level.

Effect of azolla on the growth and yield of rice plants

Z. N. Tahmida and Abdul Kader, Botany Department, University of Dhaka, Bangladesh

We evaluated azolla as a substitute for urea fertilizer for rice in a pot experiment at the Botanical Garden, University of Dhaka.

Urea was applied at 0, 25, 50, 75, and 100 kg N/ha (see table) with and without azolla. Triple superphosphate and muriate of potash, each at 50 kg/ha, were applied to all treatments except the control. Fresh azolla was inoculated 7 days after transplanting BR3 and incorporated when growth covered the pot, about 2 weeks after inoculation. Treatments were in a

randomized block design with four replications.

Azolla incorporation alone or in combination with urea stimulated rice growth and increased grain yield. Highest yield was 72.3 g/pot with 100 kg N/ha + azolla

(see table). Grain yield was similar for 75 kg N alone and 25 kg N + azolla. Azolla application also increased straw weight. Applying 75 kg N alone or 50 kg N + azolla gave the same straw yield (58 g/pot). □

Effect of azolla on rice grain and straw yield.

Treatment ^a (kg N/ha)	Av no. of grains/hill	Straw yield (g)	Grain yield (g)
No chemical fertilizer	1021	29.3	29.1
TSP + MP alone	1049	29.6	29.9
25	1478	43.0	42.1
50	1631	46.0	46.5
75	1965	58.0	56.0
100	2283	63.0	62.8
Azolla	1709	50.0	49.7
25 + azolla	1994	57.0	56.8
50 + azolla	2048	58.0	58.4
75 + azolla	2521	69.5	71.9
100 + azolla	2537	72.0	72.3

^a All treatments except the first have TSP and MP, each at 50 kg/ha.